

Effects of GPU Structuring on Accelerated Schemes of LBM and Classical CFD for Flow over a Flat Plate

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Abstract: Current trends on CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) along with high performance computing are moving towards using modern GPUs (Graphics Processing Units) in order to achieve substantial execution speedup. Consequently, it is definitely crucial to have some understanding about execution time of different computational methods and parallelization procedures. In this study, two GPU accelerated schemes namely LBM (Lattice Boltzmann Method) and SFV (Stream Function-Vorticity) formulation are investigated and compared for simulation of flow over a flat plate. The comparisons are based on solvers runtime and speedup and GPU type of structuring. On study the authors found that although the runtime for SFV formulation is less than LBM, LBM has greater potential to obtain higher speedup by using modern GPUs like NVIDIA GTX 480. In addition, a performance sensitivity is done to investigate for different GPU type of structures as a considerable parameter. The difference between GPU runtime in optimum and regular conditions indicates that using one-dimensional structuring can improve the GPU performance about 50 percent.

Key words: LBM, GPU structuring, stream function-vorticity, flat plate.

1. Introduction

GPUs (Graphics Processing Units) are specifically designed to be extremely fast at processing large graphics data sets for rendering tasks. However, in recent years due to the higher computational power of GPUs than PC-based CPUs by more than one order of magnitude, the use of the GPU in non-graphics computations has grown significantly.

Therefore, major GPU vendors have been targeting the high performance computing market with GPU hardware implementations. Software toolkits such as CUDA (Compute Unified Device Architecture), released by NVIDIA in early 2007, provide a convenient development platform that abstracts the GPU and allows access to its underlying stream computing architecture. The NVIDIA CUDA consists of several so-called MP (multiprocessors). Each MP

drives several processor cores in a SIMD (single instruction multiple data) fashion. Every MP has some registers available, as well as on-chip shared memory.

Note that there are additional cache levels available for constants and textures. Also there is a global memory of the size of the device memory which can be accessed by all threads. Due to limitations of high speed registers and shared memory and high latency of global memory, the memory access pattern is an important issue for achieving good performances.

Several schemes presented in the literature for accelerating of LBM on GPUs including using structure of arrays instead of array of structures [1], using of shared memory for propagation [2] and using of split/reversed scheme for propagation in global memory [3]. But all of the mentioned schemes lead to more complexity of computer programming. In the current study, a more simple scheme is utilized to take better address in programming with the concept of

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structure of array. The basic concept of this improvement is reducing the sensitivity of the GPU runtime versus the GPU block size. This scheme is using 1D arrays and buffers instead of 2D ones that will minimize the inter-leaved data and cause uniform streaming in global memory of the GPU. Therefore, this scheme will reduce the runtime lag according to the GPU global memory. Author's experiences show that by utilizing one-dimensional GPU arrays instead of two-dimensional ones, the speedup rate would be improved about 50 percent.

Two GPU accelerated schemes namely LBM (Lattice Boltzmann Method) and SFV (Stream Function-Vorticity) formulation using classical CFD for flow over a flat plate are investigated and compared. The comparisons are based on CPU/GPU solver runtime and speedup and GPU type of arrays used and the acceleration of the developed codes are investigated in several steps.

The first step is comparison of runtimes using GPUs, the second step is optimizing the GPU solver by using 1D arrays and buffers instead of 2D ones, and finally is the investigation of performance sensitivity for different GPU type of arrays.

In the present work, all comparisons based on runtime of solvers are performed for the same number of iteration in each method. The flat plate case has been chosen because its physical domain is rectangular which make it less complicated to utilize 1D structure arrays instead of 2D arrays. Fig. 1 shows the physical domain of a flat plate with non-uniform grids.

Both CPU and GPU versions of each solver are developed through CUDA enabled C/C+ language. The speedup ratio for different size of grid for each solver is calculated and the LBM GPU parallelizing potential is investigated in comparison with the stream function-vorticity method. Furthermore, the advantageous of each method in terms of solver runtime and speedup ratio are discussed. In addition, the capability of accelerating schemes is evaluated for different parameter sets i.e.,

Fig. 1 Physical domain of flat plate with non-uniform grids [4].

grid size, uniform or non-uniform grid and GPU parameters, such as memory, threads per block and block structure.

2. Lattice Boltzmann Method

The lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) is a novel approach in computational fluid dynamics. It appears to be an interesting alternative to the solving of the Navier-Stokes equations for various applications.

The LBM is based on a kinetic model of particle-based hydrodynamics which recovers Navier-Stokes behavior in the low Mach number limit via Chapman-Enskog expansion [5].

In terms of numerical methods, the LBM is an explicit finite difference approximation of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations with first-order accuracy in time and second order in space [6].

The most common form of the LBE (Lattice Boltzmann Equation) for a 2D lattice of type D_2Q_9 which is used in the current work can be formulated as:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x} + e_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) - f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = C_i \quad (1)$$

where f_i 's are the particle density distributions defined for a finite set of discrete particle velocity vectors (e_i ; $i = 0, \dots, 8$). These particle speeds define links among nodes on a given lattice. The collision term on the right hand side of Eq. (1) evaluated by the so-called BGK (Bhatnagar-Gross-Krook) approximation as:

$$C_i = -\frac{f_i - f_i^{eq}}{\tau} \quad (2)$$

with a single relaxation time τ . Here, f_i^{eq} is the local equilibrium distribution function that has an appropriately prescribed functional dependence on the local hydrodynamic properties. The basic hydrodynamic quantities, such as fluid density ρ and velocity \mathbf{u} , are obtained through moment summations in the velocity space,

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_i f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_i e_i f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (4)$$

In BGK approximation of LBM, the fluid kinematic viscosity ν is uniquely mapped to the relaxation time:

$$\nu = C_s^2 \left(\tau - \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

where for the particular lattice model used here $C_s = \sqrt{1/3}$ is the adiabatic speed of sound. Due to the explicit nature of the LBM, and its locality that requires only next neighbor data interactions in each time step, it is well suited for the implementation on GPUs [7].

3. Stream Function-Vorticity Formulation and Algorithm

The simulation of the two-dimensional viscous flow over a flat plate is well known problem. The fundamental equations for the stream function and vorticity are:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 \psi &= -\omega, \\ u \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} &= \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^2 \omega \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where ψ and ω are stream function and vorticity, respectively.

3.1 Uniform Grid

By considering a uniform grid and using the second-order central finite-difference discretization, the

discrete equations can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\psi_{i+1,j} - 2\psi_{i,j} + \psi_{i-1,j}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\psi_{i,j+1} - 2\psi_{i,j} + \psi_{i,j-1}}{\Delta y^2} &= -\omega_{i,j}, \\ u_{i,j} \frac{\omega_{i+1,j} - \omega_{i-1,j}}{2\Delta x} + v_{i,j} \frac{\omega_{i,j+1} - \omega_{i,j-1}}{2\Delta y} &= \\ \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\omega_{i+1,j} - 2\omega_{i,j} + \omega_{i-1,j}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\omega_{i,j+1} - 2\omega_{i,j} + \omega_{i,j-1}}{\Delta y^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

in which the spatial step sizes, Δx and Δy , can be different but they can only accept one value.

3.2 Non-uniform Grid

For solving the above equations an appropriate numerical grid is needed near the locations where large gradients exist (i.e., near the wall and trailing edge). The physical domain is mapped to computational domain such that x is mapped to ξ and y is mapped to η . The horizontal mapping formulations is:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= D \left(1 + \frac{\sinh[\beta_x (\frac{\xi}{\xi_{max}} - A)]}{\sinh(\beta_x A)} \right), \\ A &= \frac{1}{2\beta_x} \ln \frac{1 + (e^{\beta_x} - 1) (\frac{D}{L})}{1 + (e^{-\beta_x} - 1) (\frac{D}{L})} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where β_x is stretching parameter, ξ is horizontal coordinate in the computational domain, L is the total horizontal length (including flat plate itself, the length in front and behind it) and D is the horizontal physical position of the point which the clustering is desirable.

The vertical mapping formulations is:

$$y = H \frac{(\beta_y + 1) - (\beta_y - 1) \left(\frac{\beta_y + 1}{\beta_y - 1} \right)^{\left(1 - \frac{\eta}{\eta_{max}} \right)}}{1 + \left(\frac{\beta_y + 1}{\beta_y - 1} \right)^{\left(1 - \frac{\eta}{\eta_{max}} \right)}} \quad (8)$$

where β_y is stretching parameter, η is vertical coordinate in the computational domain and H is the vertical length.

Now by using the chain rule, the stream function-vorticity formulation in the computational

domain is as following:

$$\xi_x^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} + \xi_{xx} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} + \eta_y^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \eta^2} + \eta_{yy} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} = -\omega, \quad (9)$$

$$u \xi_x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \xi} + v \eta_y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \eta} = \frac{1}{Re} (\xi_x^2 \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial \xi^2} + \xi_{xx} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \xi} + \eta_y^2 \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial \eta^2} + \eta_{yy} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \eta})$$

In Eq. (9), the first and second derivative of ξ and η can be obtained analytically from Eqs. (7) and (8). By using the first-order upwind finite-difference discretization for high Reynolds numbers, the discrete equations can be obtained as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} & [2(\xi_{x_{i,j}}^2 + \eta_{y_{i,j}}^2) + SU(Re \xi_{xi,j} u_{i,j} - \xi_{xx_{i,j}}) + \\ & SV(Re \eta_{y_{i,j}} v_{i,j} - \eta_{yy_{i,j}})] \omega_{i,j} = \\ & [\xi_{x_{i,j}}^2 + SLU(Re \xi_{xi,j} u_{i,j} - \xi_{xx_{i,j}}) \omega_{i-1,j} + \\ & \xi_{x_{i,j}}^2 - SRU(Re \xi_{xi,j} u_{i,j} - \xi_{xx_{i,j}}) \omega_{i+1,j} + \\ & \eta_{y_{i,j}}^2 + SLV(Re \eta_{y_{i,j}} v_{i,j} - \eta_{yy_{i,j}}) \omega_{i,j-1} + \\ & \eta_{y_{i,j}}^2 - SRV(Re \eta_{y_{i,j}} v_{i,j} - \eta_{yy_{i,j}}) \omega_{i,j+1}] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In Eq. (10), SU , SLU , and SRU are horizontal velocity switches defined as following [4]:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{for } \frac{u_{i,j} Re}{\xi_x} \leq 2 : SLU = 0.5, SRU = 0.5, SU = SLU - SRU \\ & \text{for } \frac{u_{i,j} Re}{\xi_x} > 2 : SLU = 0.5(1 + \frac{|u|}{u}), SRU = 0.5(1 - \frac{|u|}{u}), SU = SLU - SRU \end{aligned}$$

And also SV , SLV , and SRV are vertical velocity switches defined as following [4]:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{for } \frac{v_{i,j} Re}{\eta_y} \leq 2 : SLV = 0.5, SRV = 0.5, SV = SLV - SRV \\ & \text{for } \frac{v_{i,j} Re}{\eta_y} > 2 : SLV = 0.5(1 + \frac{|v|}{v}), SRV = 0.5(1 - \frac{|v|}{v}), SV = SLV - SRV \end{aligned}$$

These equations also represent a system of non-linear equations that can be solved by Gauss-Seidel or Jacobi iterative technique. Although Gauss-Seidel is a faster algorithm for CPUs, due to its dependencies on two new calculated values, it needs appropriate technique such as shared memory for GPU programming which increases the complication of numerical code. In addition, Sperson [8] demonstrated that by using Jacobi algorithm on GPU, the convergence rate is about 50 percent faster than SSOR

algorithm on CPU. For these reasons and to have full control on GPU calculations, over relaxed Jacobi algorithm is implemented.

4. Overview of CUDA and Implementation Guidelines

CUDA is a new technology introduced by NVIDIA Corporation on February 2007 [9]. It has been created for using GPUs for non graphical purposes. CUDA allows programmer to define a new class of function, called kernels. Whenever a kernel is called, it will be executed N different CUDA thread concurrently as opposite of only once like regular C functions. In the following, GPU is referred as Device while the CPU is referred Host.

According to the LBM, local parameters are the particle density distributions defined for a finite set of discrete particle velocity vectors. These parameters must be calculated in each time step. In CPU-based program, the calculation time of these parameters is the same as other parameters. However, the explicit nature of LBM leads to the requirement of calculating of these parameters only through next neighbor data in each iteration.

Due to the locality of LBM, GPU can calculate these parameters through its faster memory and therefore LBM is more suited for the implementation on GPU. For the explicit iterative algorithm such as LBM via CUDA, there is some key issues of Device implementation. Data traffic overhead between Host and Device is one of the most important of these issues. To conquest it, the data transferring between Host and Device should be minimized for the simulation of two-dimensional viscous flow over a flat plate. Next section is devoted to analysis the different scheme consisting of SFV-UG and SFV-NUG), and lattice Boltzmann algorithm (LBM). Moreover, the effect of changing 2D arrays to 1D ones in GPU performance is investigated.

Fig. 2 shows converting the two-variable indexing to the one-variable indexing for flat plate domain. Fig. 2a

Fig. 2 Flat plate indexing with (a) 2 variable; (b) 1 variable.

shows regular indexing for 2D simulations, in which two variables (i, j) are used to identify the grid points. But for increasing performance of the GPU computing, one variable indexing is utilized, which yields to use 1D GPU structuring instead of 2D one. However, each 2D GPU structuring needs two variable indexing for identification, but by considering Fig. 2b, one variable indexing can be used for structure grids.

5. Results and Discussion

The specifications of the utilized GPU on which codes are executed are presented in Table 1. The personal computer used in this study is a regular Intel based PC equipped with an Intel Core Due 2 E7400 2.8 GHz CPU.

In order to test the implementation of the LBM and SFV formulation on the CPU and GPU, the flat plate case is used. Figs 3 and 4 show the comparisons of velocity profile and skin friction coefficient for $Re = 1500$ between the LBM and SFV formulation with GPU computations. The rise of skin friction at trailing edge of the flat plate is explained by triple-deck theory [10].

The comparisons show that LBM and stream function-vorticity results are in the good agreement. The

Table 1 Specifications of GPU Hardware [1].

Features	NVIDIA GTX 480 GPU
Number of cores	480
Memory size (MB)	1,585
Clock speed (MHz)	1,401
Memory bandwidth (GB/s)	177.4

Fig. 3 Velocity profile for $Re = 1,500$.

Fig. 4 Skin friction coefficient for $Re = 1,500$.

measured CPU solver times are compared in Table 2. The number of iterations is set to be 10^6 . The measured GPU solver times for GPU type of arrays (2D and 1D) are presented in Table 3. In this table, 2D and 1D denote two or one-dimensional GPU type of arrays, respectively.

The comparison of runtime of these schemes shows that the methods based on kinetic models like LBM need more time per iteration compared with the classic methods. But the advantage of this scheme is that it may

Table 2 Comparison between measured CPU solver runtime for different schemes (seconds).

Grid size	SFV-UG	LBM	SFV-NUG
256×128	2,688.77	6,019.40	2,769.43
512×256	14,681.70	116,636.00	12,565.19
1024×512	49,724.40	463,957.44	48,788.64

Table 3 Comparison between measured GPU solver runtime for different schemes (seconds).

Grid size	SFV-UG, 2D	LBM, 2D	SFV-NUG, 2D
256×128	118.54	418.36	118.64
512×256	437.25	1,351.79	434.07
1024×512	1,632.47	4,929.22	1,649.67
Grid size	SFV-UG, 1D	LBM, 1D	SFV-NUG, 1D
256×128	89.60	271.24	91.24
512×256	299.05	956.02	302.18
1024×512	1,152.35	3,662.54	1,150.32

need less iterations to achieve the same accuracy compared with the solver based on the SFV formulation.

However, if the comparison is based on the same number of iteration in each scheme, then the runtime for the SFV formulation is less than LBM but the potential for the LBM speedup using GPUs is better. The calculated speedups for 2D and 1D arrays are compared in Table 4.

The comparison of runtimes given in Tables 2 and 3 shows that with increasing the grid sizes, the CPU/GPU times increase by approximately linear trends. So it can be concluded that the CPU/GPU times are predictable in each method. Additional effective parameter in the GPU time is its block size when 2D or 1D GPU arrays are used. In order to investigate these parameters for this problem, the GPU times for different block size are shown in Tables 5 and 6 for 2D and 1D GPU arrays, respectively.

Table 5 shows that selecting the block size of 16×16 leads to minimum GPU runtime when 2D arrays in LBM are used. The significant disadvantage of using 2D GPU arrays is the dependency of GPU runtime on the block size. Table 6 shows that selecting the block size of 128 leads to optimum GPU runtime when 1D arrays in the LBM are used. In addition, the sensitivity on the block size for 1D GPU arrays is less than 2D

Table 4 Comparison between calculated speedup (CPU runtime/GPU runtime) for different schemes.

Grid size	SFV-UG, 2D	LBM, 2D	SFV-NUG, 2D
256×128	22.68	14.39	23.34
512×256	33.58	86.28	28.95
1024×512	30.46	94.12	29.57
Grid size	SFV-UG, 1D	LBM, 1D	SFV-NUG, 1D
256×128	30.01	22.19	30.35
512×256	49.09	122.00	41.58
1024×512	43.15	126.68	42.41

Table 5 GPU time for different block size in LBM, 2D (grid size of 1024×512).

Block size	GPU time (sec.)	$\frac{(time) - (time)_{opt}}{(time)_{opt}} \times 100$
8×8	5,561.84	12.83
16×16	4,929.22	0.00
32×32	5,151.23	4.50

Table 6 GPU time for different block size in LBM, 1D (grid size of 1024×512).

Block size	GPU time (sec.)	$\frac{(time) - (time)_{opt}}{(time)_{opt}} \times 100$
64	3,699.65	1.01
128	3,662.54	0.00
256	3,694.77	0.88

ones, which can be considered as one of the advantages of this scheme.

6. Conclusions

Several accelerated schemes of different methods of GPU programming are implemented for simulation of viscous flow over a flat plate. The comparison between these methods is accomplished in terms of speedup ratio of the LBM compared with a classic CFD solver based on the SFV formulation with uniform and non uniform grids. The performance sensitivity of each scheme is also investigated for a proposed scheme that utilizes 1D GPU array instead of 2D ones. On study the authors found that although the runtime for SFV formulation is less than LBM, the potential for LBM speedup using GPUs is better and by using 1D GPU arrays speedup up to about 120x is achievable. It is demonstrated that CPU/GPU times have approximately linear trend and they can be predictable in each method. The results on optimum value of GPU

parameters show that the sensitivity on the block size for 1D GPU arrays is less than 2D ones, that is another advantage of the proposed scheme.

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